

BEHAVIOUR OF THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES WITH HOLES MACHINED USING A THERMALLY-ASSISTED PIERCING PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

Thermally-Assisted Piercing (TAP) is an alternative method, to conventional machining techniques, of producing holes in Thermoplastic Composites (TPCs). The technique is designed to be sympathetic to the continuous fibres within composite structures. This can help retain more of the original structural efficiency that make composite materials attractive to so many industries. The aim of the current work is to investigate how key process variables affect the mechanical performance of pierced specimens. Open-hole tension and compression tests were conducted and show that improvements of 5% and 12%, respectively, can be achieved for the smallest heated areas used for piercing. Increasing the heated area reduced the performance of the tension and compression tested specimens. The compression specimens showed a greater reduction in strength for the increase in heated area. This observation supports the suggestion that fibre waviness dominates the performance of the specimens when varying the diameter of the heated area used for piercing.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fibre Reinforced Plastics (FRPs) have become increasingly popular within many industries attempting to improve structural efficiencies and achieve weight savings. The use of FRPs, with high strength and stiffness to weight ratios, allows lighter structures to be manufactured without trading off mechanical performance. Despite the mechanical advantages that can be gained by using FRPs instead of conventional materials, there are still many barriers that prevent this step change being implemented by some industry sectors. One of these barriers is the cost and complexity of manufacturing and processing FRPs.

Thermosetting Composites (TSCs) have been more commonly used for structures due to their increased mechanical properties over Thermoplastic Composites (TPCs). This structural efficiency advantage has, previously, been the primary factor for TSC popularity over TPCs. TPCs can be heated and processed/formed using similar techniques to those applied when working sheet metal. This has become an attractive prospect for high volume manufacturing industries e.g. automotive and single aisle aircraft production.

The application of TPCs has recently increased due to the ability to increase production efficiencies and reduce manufacturing costs. The ability to melt the thermoplastic matrix also makes TPCs more attractive for welded joints and potential re-cycling of structures – a growing factor for many industries. Although TPCs can be welded it is almost inevitable that, as with TSCs, they will require bonding or mechanical fastening to other components.

Mechanical fastening, adhesive bonding and welding are all potential methods of joining TPCs to construct larger assemblies. Mechanical fastenings are usually adopted for applications that require disassembly or progressive and reliable failure. The majority of fastening systems are accepted by a

recess or hole within the structure to make an interlock. All currently used machining methods for fastener holes (e.g. drilling, water-jet cutting and laser machining) rely on material removal techniques that cut and remove load bearing fibres.

As an alternative to machining, material displacement processes can be applied to composites to create holes for fastening without removing the load carrying fibres from the structure. Moulding-in holes is a method used to displace fibres around an insert and into the surrounding volume to retain the load carrying fibre paths. The retention of fibre continuity around the hole permits higher open-hole and bearing strength through a reduction in stress concentrations around the hole when compared to conventional drilling [1] [2].

Thermally-Assisted Piercing (TAP) is another technique that can be used to create holes in TPCs [3]. This material displacement technique transports fibres away from the desired hole location, rather than cutting and removing them completely. The re-processing ability of TPCs allows this technique to be applied at various stages within the manufacture of components to retain fibre continuity [4]. The aim of the current investigation is to build on previous work and identify how key process variables within TAP affect the resultant mechanical properties of pierced specimens.

This paper briefly describes the TAP technique used to create specimens for mechanical testing. Open-hole tension and compression tests are described and the results of testing pierced and drilled specimens are presented. Results are compared and discussed for various diameters of the heated area when piercing, using the drilled specimens as the baseline, with future work outlined.

2 THERMALLY-ASSISTED PIERCING (TAP)

Previous work included a feasibility study of the TAP process using a preliminary prototype piercing rig [3]. For the current study a new TAP rig was manufactured with flexibility to vary the process variables (Figure 1). The heated area, temperature when piercing, clamping pressure and spike geometry can be varied before piercing. The equipment uses pneumatic actuators to clamp the laminate throughout the process and to drive the piercing spike once the laminate is heated sufficiently.

The piercing process for all combinations of variables relied on four key stages: initial rig heat-up, clamped laminate heating, piercing and cool-down (Figure 2 a-d). The heated area is varied by attaching tooling surfaces that conduct the heat from the heater units. The previous piercing rig used an induction heating method for rapid, non-contact, heating. This was changed to a conduction method for the current rig in order to accurately control the heated area when piercing. Future industrial application may find it advantageous to revert to an induction heating method for energy efficiency and process speed advantages.

The tooling surfaces vary in diameter according to the size of heated area required. An insulating surface was integrated to mask the heater units for tests that required heated areas smaller than the size of the heater units. A final insulating ring was placed around the heater units and provided a constant overall clamping area for the tests.

Figure 1: Thermally-assisted piercing rig.

The composite specimens used for testing were manufactured from carbon fibre reinforced Polyetheretherketone (CF/PEEK) (Tenax® TPUD PEEK-HTS40) pre-impregnated unidirectional tape. A 21 ply lay-up provided nominally 2.9 mm thick, balanced and symmetric, laminates $[(0/90)_5 / \bar{0}]_s$, which were pressed at 400°C under a consolidation pressure of 0.91 MPa. The pressure was applied for one minute per ply (21 minutes for the laminate) before deactivating the heat input and allowing the laminate to cool under the consolidation pressure to room temperature (with an approximate cooling rate of 1.7 °C/min).

Figure 2: Schematic diagram of the 4 key piercing process stages: a) Initial rig heat-up, b) Clamped laminate heating, c) Piercing and d) Cool-down.

The temperature and clamping pressure used when piercing were similar to the original laminate manufacturing conditions. The spike geometry remained the same throughout the current experiments, 30° inclusive angle (Figure 3) with a 6 mm diameter circular shaft (producing a 6 mm diameter hole – Figure 4).

Figure 3: Schematic diagram of piercing spike.

Figure 4: Photograph of pierced specimen.

3 OPEN-HOLE TESTING

3.1 Introduction

Open-hole tension and compression tests were conducted to determine the mechanical performance of pierced specimens with varying size of heated area. Testing was performed on a 250 kN, screw-driven Instron using hydraulic grips and a constant displacement rate of 1 mm/min to ultimate failure of the specimens. Specimens were nominally 36 mm wide with 6 mm holes, and either 200 mm or 125 mm long for tension or compression tests, respectively.

The current study investigated the effect of varying the heated area on the open-hole performance of pierced specimens. The diameter of the heated area was increased from a baseline value (D) by 50% (to $1.5 D$) and then by another 50% of the original diameter (to $2 D$). Testing was conducted on 5 specimens for each size of heated area.

3.2 Open-hole tension results

Figure 5 shows the ultimate strength of the pierced specimens plotted as percentages of the drilled specimen strength. The results show that for the baseline heated area diameter (D) the ultimate strength of the specimens was approximately 105% of the drilled specimen strength. Increasing the diameter of the heated area by 50% (to $1.5 D$) showed no difference in the ultimate strength of the specimens. Increasing the heated area diameter to $2 D$ reduced the strength of the pierced specimens slightly to 101% of the drilled hole strength.

A possible explanation of these results is the following. Increasing the heated area diameter increased the length of fibre that was free to move during piercing. This is likely to cause increased fibre waviness which would have a tendency to reduce the mechanical performance when compared with

the smaller heated area. During the piercing process fibres are displaced and compacted into the heated volume to create a hole (increasing fibre volume fraction). Reducing the heated area is, therefore, likely to increase the packing of fibres since the same volume of fibres are displaced into a smaller heated volume.

Figure 5: Open-hole tensile strength of pierced specimen as a percentage of drilled specimens (varying diameter of heated area).

3.3 Open-hole compression results

The open-hole compression strengths of pierced specimens, as percentages of drilled specimens, are shown for varying diameter of heated area in Figure 6. The results show that for the baseline diameter of the heated area (D) the pierced specimen strength was 112% of the drilled specimen strength. Increasing the heated area to 1.5 D decreased the pierced specimen strength to 104% of the drilled specimen strength and a further increase in heated area to 2 D produced a decrease in the strength of pierced specimens to 79% of the drilled hole strength.

Figure 6: Open-hole compressive strength of pierced specimens as a percentage of drilled specimens (varying diameter of heated area).

The open-hole compression tests show a significant trend: increasing the heated area reduced the ultimate strength of the specimens. This agrees with the results of the open-hole tension tests that show a modest reduction in strength with increasing heated area size. Compression tests are more sensitive to fibre waviness due to the onset of fibre buckling. It is, therefore, likely that an increase in fibre waviness for the larger heated areas has led to larger reductions in strength under compression. The effect of reduced fibre packing (and hence volume fraction) for larger heated volumes during piercing is also likely to have contributed to the observed reduction in strength for increasing diameter of heated area.

4 CONCLUDING REMARKS

The size of the heated area when piercing can have a significant effect on the ultimate strength of pierced specimens under open-hole loading. The ultimate tensile strength of pierced specimens was 105% of the drilled hole strength for a baseline heated area and increasing the heated area led to a small reduction in strength. For compression testing, the maximum compressive strength of pierced specimens was initially 112% of the drilled specimen strength for the smallest heated area, but doubling the heated area led to a 43% strength reduction from this value.

The results in this study show that the open-hole strength of specimens can be improved by reducing the size of the heated area. It is suggested that reducing the size of the heated area both constrains the fibre waviness to a smaller volume of material and increases the fibre packing (and hence fibre volume fraction); consequently, the open-hole strength is higher for smaller heated areas. Future work aims to quantify the waviness and local volume fractions within pierced specimens and investigate the sensitivity of strength to other process variables.

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